

SUPERNOVA

Deliverable 8.2

About SUPERNOVA

EC-Grant Agreement	101146883
Program	HORIZON EUROPE
Start date	01 April 2024
Duration	42 months

Supernova will aim to **increase the O&M grid-friendly design of solar PV plants** thanks to advanced software solutions that are evolving the planning, design, and operation of solar PV systems.

The project will take a **multi-layered approach**, integrating individual solutions into interoperable digital platforms, and utilises the power of AI tools to efficiently manage and control huge amounts of data.

SUPERNOVA will also focus on **data sharing** as a means of creating mutual benefit for providers and users.

Goals

1 Improving the design of solar plants with data for increased performance, reliability, security, and flexibility

2 Developing tools and components for different sensor technologies to be adaptable to different environments

3 Using robotic solutions to reduce costs, increase data collection, and automate the process

4 Using data fusion to generate insights and improve reliability via solar PV asset management software

5 Developing methodology to classify solar components based on big data and artificial intelligence

6 Increasing the profitability of solar PV systems via operation & maintenance (O&M), and grid-friendly strategies

7 Creating confidence and business value in sharing solar PV data

Visual identity

The development of the project's CDE strategy was initiated with the design of SUPERNOVA's visual identity, including a **logo**, guidelines and communication materials.

The name SUPERNOVA was selected based on the concept of "**data explosion**". It stands for: Operation and Maintenance and Grid Friendly Tools and Solutions for Solar Data Fusion and Insight Explosion for Reliable, Bankable, Circular PV Plants.

Logo

The SUPERNOVA logo represents the O&M and grid friendly design to enable increased performance, reliability, security and flexibility of PV plants. The letter print of the word SUPERNOVA is supposed to resemble the font of programming language and emphasizes that the project aims to develop data driven improvements.

SUPERNOVA

SUPERNOVA

Templates

MS-Word (*.doc)

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Authors: Author1 (Partner short name); Author2 (Partner short name)

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SUPERNOVA

Press release

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Questions? Get in touch
Name Surname@mail.com

Discover more on:

supernova-pv.eu

MS-PowerPoint (*.ppt)

Promotional materials

Project Leaflet

See you on our website

supernova-pv.eu
@SUPERNOVA

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Reliable · Bankable · Circular

SUPERNOVA is a European funded project aiming to establish quality and a high-performance for solar photovoltaic projects

We have three objectives

Improving the design of solar plants to increase performance, reliability, security and flexibility

Developing tools and components for different sensor technologies

Using robotic solutions to reduce costs, increase data collection, and automate the process

Goals

- 1 Improving the design of solar plants with data for increased performance, reliability, security, and flexibility
- 2 Developing tools and components for different sensor technologies to be adaptable to different environments
- 3 Using robotic solutions to reduce costs, increase data collection, and automate the process
- 4 Using data fusion to generate insights and improve reliability via solar photovoltaic asset management software
- 5 Developing methodology to classify solar components based on big data and artificial intelligence
- 6 Increasing the profitability of solar photovoltaic systems via operation & maintenance, and grid-friendly strategies
- 7 Creating confidence and business value in sharing solar photovoltaic data

Rollup

Reliable · Bankable · Circular

SUPERNOVA is a European funded project aiming to establish quality and a high-performance for solar photovoltaic projects

See you on our website

supernova-pv.eu
@SUPERNOVA

Partners

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To learn more

→ supernova-pv.eu
in @supernova

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PRESENTED BY: LongName LongSurname, longname.longsurname@university.com

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Website

Homepage - Supernova

www.supernova-pv.eu

About

On this page: [Goals](#) [Importance](#) [Partners](#)

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The project will take a **multi-layered approach**, integrating individual solutions into interoperable digital platforms, and utilise the power of AI tools to efficiently manage and control huge amounts of data.

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News & Events

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EVENT

SUPERNOVA project launch in Italy

On 11-12 April, we launched our SUPERNOVA project at the NOI Techpark, at Bolzano, Italy.

Project Results

24 Oct 24

Cybersecurity and grid-friendly requirements position paper

The objectives of this publication is to define the cybersecurity requirements for technical tools developed within the SUPERNOVA project. This document will also provide an overview of the regulatory framework (current and upcoming) for cybersecurity in the solar PV sector in Europe,

Social Media

LinkedIn: SUPERNOVA

LinkedIn posts

- Cybersecurity and grid-friendly guidelines:
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/supernovahorizoneurope_read-supernovas-new-cybersecurity-paper-activity-7255223174752038912-sB-h?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
- SUPERNOVA LinkedIn launch:
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/supernovahorizoneurope_solar-flexibility-ai-activity-7252646097951551489-9YM9?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

SUPERNOVA
Horizon Europe funded project, aiming to establish quality and a high-performance for PV projects.
Solar Electric Power Generation · 80 followers · 0-1 employees

✓ Following Message ⋮

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Overview

SUPERNOVA is a Horizon Europe funded project, aiming to establish quality and a high-performance for solar photovoltaic projects. The project aims to improve the design of solar plants for increased performance, reliability, security and flexibility; develop tools and components for different sensor technologies; and employ robotic solutions to reduce costs, increase data collection, and automate the process.

EVERPV has gathered a consortium of 20 partners from across the entire solar industry value chain.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101146883.

Website
<https://supernova-pv.eu/>

eurac
research

∴ **csem**

sicame
GROUP

tecnal:a
MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH
& TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE

••••• **Zelestra**

The logo for SUPERNOVA features a blue diamond-shaped icon to the left of the text 'SUPERNOVA' in a blue, sans-serif font.